

DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY OF MSME IN LANGSA CITY (RESEARCH WITH PENTA HELIX APPROACH)

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Abstract

Industry 4.0 in Langsa City is a development in the economic field, namely digitalization, collaboration with MSMEs in Langsa City with industrial growth near technology. The role of stakeholders in the Pentahelix model and Digital Entrepreneurship development strategy for MSMEs in Langsa City. This study uses a SWOT analysis of academics, entrepreneurs, government, society, and media conducted in Langsa City. The results of this study are to expand the reach of consumers and the number of specifications globally to enter the ASEAN (MEA) market and join e-commerce services to get cheap promotions and increase the expansion of reach and specifications with digital technology. E-commerce can improve the performance of MSMEs.

Keywords: MSMEs, Digital Entrepreneurship, SWOT Analysis, Penta Helix

INTRODUCTION

In this digital era or known as the 4.0 era, business actors, especially in Langsa City, which is currently developing, must continue to receive full attention and support from the government in various aspects, as stated in Law Number 20 of 2008 concerning Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises and Medium (MSME) Digital. The government has made efforts to improve access and transfer of technology to develop innovative MSME actors, among others, by utilizing Information and Communication Technology (ICT) so that it is hoped that they will be able to compete with other MSME actors. MSMEs not only provide product catalogs and promotions on their websites, such as Facebook, Instagram, and others, but MSME sites have been used as a means for dialogue, discussion, and consultation with consumers online, displaying bulletin boards, making electronic questionnaires, mailing lists, and coordinating through electronic mail (email) and WhatsApp (Ruston). Currently, the marketing of company products and services is an interactive process due to the use of information technology.

The development of the industrial economy 4.0 often becomes unfriendly to MSMEs, which also have an essential role in economic resilience and challenges that business actors, especially MSMEs, cannot avoid. MSMEs must adapt to industrial developments increasingly sided by the side with technology. A breakthrough regarding the product is a must to be recognized and survive in such a large market. Change 4.0 is an integrated roadmap to implement strategies in dealing with the industrial revolution 4.0, including technology, system concepts, thinking paradigms, and not to forget the quality of products that are qualified from the results of their efforts. MSMEs need a lot of improvement, especially in mastering technology which is the key to determining competitiveness in the industrial era 4.0. Therefore, digital developments in the 4.0 period will positively impact MSME entrepreneurs if they can manage them well to compete with foreign entrepreneurs from other countries.

In this developing country, many entrepreneurs have sprung up, but among them, many still lack knowledge about digital. Even in this sophisticated era, digitalization is very helpful in product marketing. Digital marketing can increase the competitiveness of entrepreneurs, especially MSMEs in Langsa City. Innovations must have specific advantages in the form of output based on local wisdom at relatively affordable prices, easy labor, simple skills, unique product specifications, have an international market, and, no less critical, must be creative (Daulay, 2018).

Marketing difficulties faced by business actors include (1) products, such as having control over how products and details are presented to customers. Not infrequently, business owners use the services of professional models and photographers to help create the desired promotional images. But in the early days of the marketplace, the business owner had little control over the product being presented. The problem is that many sellers are still in the learning stage, so it is difficult to create good photography and imitate the required features. Concerning customer service, conventional e-commerce stores have a centralized customer management system that makes it easy to meet customer needs. But in the marketplace, buyers who are not happy with the product or service of a seller will usually direct complaints to the market, not the seller. This persistent problem often escalates into social media problems or attacks, (2) technology, and online customers will avoid websites that often experience hardships and do not provide adequate purchase security. Investing in dedicated servers, security options, and continuous technology updates can address the latest security threats. Therefore, building a solid online brand and maintaining customer trust is important.

Business actors have attended several pieces of training from institutions to provide understanding in advertising/promotions and creating online content. However, there are still many that are lacking in the use of digital, which impacts MSME actors in Langsa City. It is challenging to develop their marketing using digital. The internet and information technology should be used to expand and enhance traditional marketing functions. This definition concentrates on all conventional marketing. We can also state that opinions such as “interactive marketing,” “one-to-one marketing,” and “e-marketing” are closely related to “digital marketing.”

Surveys and field interviews of business actors (MSMEs) obtained the voice of online customers as follows: MSMEs have limited knowledge about the internet and online marketing. For the smooth running and development of their business, MSMEs ask to be given training and assistance to independently use ICT, including providing facilities and infrastructure. This is due to the limited knowledge of MSMEs. MSME awareness of e-commerce products is still low (31.67%), and there are few communities, making it challenging to develop a business. From some of these problems, there is a very dominant weakness. Namely, the digital MSMEs of Langsa City have not run optimally as planned, both in the provision of facilities and infrastructure as well as in collaboration with other parties (Setiawan, 2011). The gap between the communities that have only limited the use of products in the environment has not been maximized in the development of MSMEs. Moreover, it is limited to taking samples from various products and advertising/promotions.

In running and developing a business in the digital era, there are still several obstacles, including government policies that have not been in favor of the creative community; the government is not yet maximal in carrying out its functions because there is no direct reach by MSMEs. After all, it is still found that there are business actors who have not been registered, and the government is still lacking in data collection and a forum for market development that is considered adequate and not burdensome from costs, places and services; creative industry development has not been optimal, mainly due to the lack of industrial attractiveness, immature creative industry business models, and business risks that must face, content development, creation, and innovative technology are not yet optimal, mainly due to inadequate internet infrastructure, performance building infrastructure not yet optimal. Meet standards, expensive production machines, expensive software producing innovative products and services, lack of content research, and lack of content archiving activities. The progress of the creative economy needs the role of the Langsa City government as the creative economy can positively impact the economic progress of Langsa City.

We should not waste the rise of this creative economy. The government needs to facilitate by providing markets and factors of production. Economic policies taken should also be in favor of the progress of the creative economy. A government that can accommodate the interests of innovative economic development, quality human resources, and a solid network (network formation) between creative economy actors, technology practitioners, and the government. Because creativity and technology are a process that must always be side by side, training is also needed, but it is not enough to train. How can there be a coaching process to develop a business well to have competitiveness? Therefore, in this study, the author offers the concept of the Penta Helix.

THEORITICAL REVIEW

Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship is a pretty old profession in this world. An entrepreneur (entrepreneur) is someone who takes the risk of an agreement with a certain amount of money specified in the contract. The domain has existed since the exchange of goods or barter in everyday life and continued after the discovery of a means of selling goods called coins, either with gold standard or paper money.

Entrepreneurship is not a magical science that brings money in an instant but rather a science, art, and skill to manage all limited available resources, information, and funds to maintain life, earn a living or reach the top position in a career (Hendro, 2011).

Digital

Digital is a concept of understanding the times regarding technology and science, from everything manual to automatic and everything complex to concise. Digital is a challenging and flexible method that makes it a staple in human life. Digital theory is always related to media.

New media is currently developing in the context of technology, information, and communication. Modern media is the umbrella of life that connects humans with humans and technology in this century. Examples of modern media/new media: Internet, Mobile Phones, Social Network, and Web.

Implementation of new media is a terminology to explain the convergence between digital technology that is computerized and connected to the network. Technology is one of the main factors causing changes in various fields. Technology makes distance and space (the world is flat; Thomas Friedman). Everything is closer and transparent (Awaluddin, 2015).

Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs)

Small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) are currently able to place themselves as one of the main priorities for the government in their development. The existence of efforts from government policies in developing MSMEs is not new and has even been proclaimed for a long time. Various parties have contributed to advancing MSMEs, such as the efforts of several ministries to jointly develop MSMEs, such as the policy of the Ministry of Cooperatives and MSMEs, which has launched the National Entrepreneurial Movement (GWN) by increasing the role of MSMEs (Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises) in 2009. Bank Indonesia by providing products for MSMEs such as KUR (People's Business Credit) with no prestige. These various policies are carried out to be able quickly so that entrepreneurs can grow and develop in Indonesia, especially in the field of MSMEs.

Digital-based SMEs cannot be separated from digital marketing or digital marketing, a form of effort to promote and market a "brand" using digital media, such as the internet. This marketing is digital marketing, a viral strategy most marketers use worldwide. The impact of the increasing world of the internet and technology makes the internet a very prospective market. The entry of MSMEs into the e-commerce market creates an increased image and can create marketing networks more quickly (Janshahi, 2013).

Penta Helix

Remodelling the economic and market development models created (Carayannis, 2014). The strategy model will involve elements of the creative economy Penta Helix, namely ABCGM (Academics, Business Sector, Communities, Government, and Media): Academics, Business Sector, Community, Government, and Media. The Penta Helix element was originally a Triple Helix with aspects of Academics, Business Sector, Government, which then added with one part, Civil Society (or Communities in this study), to become a Quadruple Helix to accommodate the community's perspective. In this case, a "media and culture-based society" has also become an integral part of innovation in today's 21st Century.

Furthermore, the Communities element opens up opportunities for cross-disciplinary configuration and networking, frees the concept of "innovation" from just economic considerations and goals, and involves creativity as part of the knowledge and innovation production process. Added this Quadruple Helix one more element, namely Media, because in the context of developing the creative economy in Indonesia, the Media (both conventional

media and social media) hold a significant role (Colapinto, 2012). However, it remains an independent element or is not directly affected by other aspects of its parts and functions.

Figure 1 Penta Helix Model

In this study, a conceptual framework can be made that can be used as a basis for this research; it can be stated that the Penta helix approach (Academics, Business Sector, Community, Government, in determining digital entrepreneurship development strategies with an overview of this conceptual framework can be as follows:

Figure 2: Conceptual Framework

From the conceptual framework, it is illustrated that the Penta Helix model (Academics, Business Sector, Community, Government, and Media in the future can provide their respective roles for strengthening digital entrepreneurship, which is focused on digital-based MSMEs in Langsa City and is expected to synergize or offer a new idea or idea). Using a swot strategy will result in strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and challenges.

RESEARCH METHODS

Research Approach

The type of research used in this study is an inductive qualitative method: collecting, compiling, and describing various data and basic information. The material obtained will be interpreted in the form of exposure and analysis to achieve this research's objectives.

Qualitative research is based on post positivism philosophy, which views social reality as something complete, complex, dynamic, and full of meaning, and the relationship of symptoms is interactive (reciprocal) (Sugiyono, 2017). In qualitative research, the information collected and processed must remain objective and not be influenced by the researcher's opinion. This research focuses on case studies and detailed research on an object during a specific period carried out completely, thoroughly, and in-depth using various data sources.

Data Analysis

Data analysis is done manually. The analytical method that the researcher uses in analyzing the data is descriptive qualitative. It presents the data in written form and explains it according to the needs of the data from the research results, which are then analyzed. So in this data analysis, researchers will describe the application of digital entrepreneurship marketing strategies in Langsa City registered with Disperindagkop and SMEs that are heard and seen without reducing it.

Data analysis in this study is descriptive qualitative data analysis. Qualitative data analysis is the presentation of data in written form and explains what it is by the data obtained from the research results. As for the data to be analyzed, where some of the qualitative data acquired will be quantified/replaced to facilitate the merging of two or more variable data, then after the final results are received, they will be re-qualified.

Determine the company's position to determine the status of SMEs in Langsa City registered with the Department of Industry, Trade, Cooperatives, and SMEs from growth and market share. If the position is known, it will be able to determine what marketing strategy can be done by the company. In this study, the data analysis tool used was SWOT analysis (Strength, Weakness, Opportunities, and Threats), especially to find strategies to increase MSMEs in Langsa City and register with the Langsa City Cooperatives and MSMEs Office.

SWOT analysis compares the external factors of opportunities (Opportunities) and threats (Threats) with internal elements of strengths (Strengths) and weaknesses (Weaknesses) which results in the choice of strategies as shown below:

Figure 3: Choice of Strategies in SWOT Analysis

The SWOT method is used to formulate qualitatively and holistically the internal and external environment of the observed object. In the inner scope, the analysis will explain in detail the aspects of the business's weaknesses and strengths. Meanwhile, in the outer content, this analysis will explain in detail the elements of opportunities (opportunities) and obstacles/threats/challenges (threats) the business will face.

Table 1: SWOT Analysis Matrix

	STRENGTH (S)	WEAKNESSES (W)
OPPORTUNITIES (O)	SO Strategy: Using all the strengths you have to take advantage of the opportunities that exist	Strategi WO: Overcome all weaknesses by taking advantage of an opportunity exists.
THREATS (T)	Strategi ST: Using all power for avoid threats	Strategi WT: Suppress all weaknesses and prevent threats

If the strategy in Figure 3 is associated with a business strategy, the business strategy choices that need to be made are as follows (Rangkuti, 2015):

1. SO (Strengths-Opportunities) strategy, in this situation, the company needs to conduct aggressive business development to take advantage of considerable strengths to create new or develop existing businesses. The strategy in the SO quadrant is referred to as an aggressive strategy.
2. ST (Strengths-Threats) strategy, in this situation, the company needs to diversify its product business by developing superior products. The strategy in the ST quadrant is referred to as a diversification strategy.
3. WO (Weaknesses-Opportunities) strategy, in this situation, management must analyze the weaknesses to eliminate the primary defects. The system in the WO quadrant is referred to as a reverse strategy.
4. WT (Weaknesses-Threats) strategy, management must analyze the main weaknesses that exist while avoiding threats. The strategy in the WT quadrant is referred to as a defensive

strategy. After analyzing all the variables above, the internal and internal factors are outlined in the diagram.

The steps carried out in analyzing the strategy above are as follows:

- a. Collecting data, namely data collected from observations, interviews, and documentation studies.
- b. Clarifying the data material, this step is used to select data that can be used as a reference for further research.
- c. Clarifying the data material is done by grouping the data obtained from observations, interviews, and documentation studies.
- d. Editing, namely conducting a review of the data collected through the techniques used, then conducting research and checking the truth, and correcting if there are errors to facilitate the process of further investigation.
- e. Presenting data, that is, existing data, is described verbally, given logical explanations and descriptions, and can draw arguments and conclusions.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

SWOT Analysis Results

Internal Strength Factor

1. Langsa City digital SMEs can expand consumer reach

The Go Online 8 Million Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSME) Facilitation Program aim to create eight million Indonesian MSMEs to enter the online market platform starting mid-2017. This activity aims to open up new market opportunities for MSMEs in Indonesia, both regionally and globally. In 2018, the government began to carry out four stages in collaboration with relevant ministries/agencies: onboarding or encouraging offline MSME actors to go online and active selling or mentoring to MSMEs. They have gone online to increase online transactions, scale up a business or help MSME actors to improve their business scale, Go International, or a movement to encourage MSME actors to expand market reach internationally. By combining online and offline sales systems, MSME businesses are expected to reach more consumers in the hope of increasing sales potential.

2. Langsa City digital MSMEs can estimate the number of customers

Langsa City digital MSMEs (digital marketing) broadly have the same target as conventional marketing, namely the target for prospective consumers to buy the products you offer directly; the use of Langsa City digital MSMEs can reach all people, anytime, anywhere, and in a different way. Whatever. Of course, it is far superior to conventional marketing, which is only limited in time, location, and user reach. Digital marketing users such as SEO (Search Engine Optimization) techniques on the Google search engine, advertisements in online media, to ads on social media will undoubtedly be able to reach a reasonably broad consumer.

3. MSME e-commerce services are equipped with payment solution services

E-commerce is a new field for the trade industry in this era of globalization. The e-commerce industry in Indonesia is starting to show very rapid development. The existence of e-commerce in Indonesia is already felt, so the competition is fierce to be top mind in the eyes of the public. E-commerce is electronic commerce, the marketing of goods or services with an electronic system via the internet. In this case, e-commerce has content that involves data/system/management that is executed automatically. This industry will include fund transfers, online marketing, buying, and selling, etc. E-commerce is part of e-business, where the scope of e-business is more comprehensive, not just commerce but also includes collaborating with business partners, customer service, job vacancies, and others, all of which are supported by technology.

Internal Weakness Factor

1. MSMEs have limitations on online marketing

Most MSME products are marketed, so their reach is not yet widespread. Many parties encourage MSMEs to penetrate the global market. Some SMEs themselves also have a dream to sell their products to international markets. Unfortunately, limited knowledge about online marketing is still a significant obstacle. Online marketing is indeed a solution to reach a broader market. Utilization of information technology among MSME actors is knowledge of internet technology and the extent to which internet technology is used to support the business being occupied.

User understanding of IT will determine the success of an information system. Otherwise, the user's ignorance or anxiety about the new system can cause failure in using IT. Increased user understanding of information systems also affects the success of utilizing IT. MSME owners with a background in marketing and sales can accept that businesses apply IT for competitive advantage. However, MSMEs generally do not have a section that explicitly manages IT. Generally, MSMEs rely more on external assistance to carry out activities related to the use of digital-based IT. Dependence on external parties will be reduced when MSME owners have a sufficient understanding of IT through the learning process. With a high knowledge of technology, it is hoped that MSME owners will adopt and utilize IT extensively. The low level of understanding of MSME business actors.

2. Langsa City digital SMEs have not run optimally with the Penta helix concept

In developing MSMEs, cooperation between relevant stakeholders is needed. A strategic approach is required to establish MSMEs by involving various parties' participation to realize MSME progress. The Penta Helix model with the ABCGM formula, which stands for Academy, Business, Community, Government, and Media, is suitable to be used as a model for cooperation in MSME development programs related to various sectors in the business processes being carried out. Hence, it requires the roles of multiple stakeholders. The success of the MSME development program depends on how the stakeholders carry out the program according to their primary functions. MSME development also depends on how the

government can collaborate with various stakeholders to realize MSME progress in the future. The lack of social influence factors from the community of fellow MSMEs and the lack of support for facilities and infrastructure and experts from the related MSME supervisors. Electronic commerce (e-commerce) is a marketing and sales service that can do online on internet.

3. The number of wifi.id access points, as an alternative, need to be increased

Lack of infrastructure provision in the form of installation/addition of wifi.id access points, such as the lack of preparing a 3G/4G network and preparing MangoSTAR (satellite) services as an internet access solution for MSMEs located in areas that have not been reached by cable, fiber, or mobile services, which can later make it difficult. They are organizing training in addition to technical material on ICT and e-commerce products and business insights to foster an entrepreneurial spirit where the curriculum is adjusted to the level of SMEs in ICT adoption.

External Opportunity Factor

1. The ASEAN free market (MEA) is an opportunity for Langsa City MSMEs to expand the market

The era of free markets in the ASEAN region (AFTA), commonly known as the ASEAN Economic Community (AEC), has been echoed by the government since 2015. This free trade aims to create a single market and unified production in the ASEAN region, where the flow of goods such as service products, production, investment, and capital will enter freely. In this free market, the elimination of tariffs for trade between ASEAN countries is also enforced. The ASEAN free market that is currently running provides many benefits for domestic MSME business players. MSMEs have an excellent opportunity to profit in this free market, where the government offers many conveniences and facilities for MSME business owners. Business capital assistance from the Indonesian Chamber of Commerce and Industry in the Banking and Financial Sector aims to provide venture capital assistance to SME businesses that have export potential.

2. The use of digital technology can improve the performance of MSMEs in Langsa City, among others, increasing access to new customers domestically and abroad as well as increasing sales

The benefits of using social media that have been identified are that it allows MSME business actors to gain access to new customers. MSME business players realize that the information provided or shared in social media application accounts can quickly spread to various groups of consumers. With viral information that is applied, MSME business people can get customers who are geographically far away. It will be challenging to reach conventional communication media with regional boundaries, such as newspapers or local radio. The features provided in social media applications also allow MSME business players to transact more efficiently with customers and suppliers. Customers can order products through various features on social media.

3. The cost of promotion through digital media is cheaper than the cost of advertising that must be spent in the traditional way (offline)

Most MSME business people feel the benefits of product/service promotion from using social media applications. The efficiency offered by social media applications for MSME business actors is one of the main reasons for their use. MSME business actors also believe advertising products or services in social media applications to be more attractive than when using conventional media. Information in the form of attractive and creative pictures, graphics, photos and videos can be made by MSME business actors themselves. Information with an attractive appearance can make product/service promotion more effective.

External Threat Factors

1. Langsa City SMEs find it challenging to develop their business because of limited capital

Loan funds or capital are closely related to MSME actors because, in addition to business development, money is also believed to increase the turnover of business actors. Most MSME actors face capital problems for business development. Must put new business ideas for business expansion away. The root of this capital problem is classic. MSME actors are often judged to be unable to meet banking requirements.

2. Transaction security is a primary consideration

People are increasingly confident in conducting digital transactions in today's digital era. Many facts show how active the Indonesian people are in digital commerce, such as sharing information on social media and the rapid development of transactions in the e-commerce industry, whose value is estimated to continue to increase. The transactions in question are not only financial transactions but also data/information transactions that are streamed through online channels.

3. The availability of internet access is still minimal

IP Address is one of the internet resources that are limited in number and is the only internet network experience system. This experience system allows communication between networks on the internet. The crisis of limited availability of allocations is feared to be an obstacle to internet growth and contributes to reducing Indonesia's competitiveness. The biggest challenge is how to increase the accessibility of MSMEs to go digital and increase MSME capabilities to produce products that compete with foreign products that have flooded Indonesian e-commerce. Important considering that most MSMEs live in rural areas with minimal internet access, and many are not yet digital-literate. The limitations of the lack of internet result in not maximal sales made by business actors because often internet limitations prevent business actors from interacting or the needs of companies / MSME actors to market products will connect these official accounts to all social media companies/business actors.

Discussion

MSMEs will still be able to grow and develop. Still, on the other hand, if you look closely, the weakness of MSMEs is that they will not be able to build their business if they do not get

capital assistance to compete. These weaknesses, such as lack of capital, managerial skills, and unhealthy competition, result in a reduced scope of business that is difficult to resolve in the short term, even though the government has deployed policies to support MSMEs. However, the fact is that MSMEs have been able to help the economy in each region because the development of MSMEs is considered to reduce poverty levels by creating job vacancies.

Developments in the digital world have brought about a new change in information exchange, trade, social networking, and global communication that makes the world feel in the palm of your hand. The use of social media for MSMEs is extensive. All MSMEs sampled in this study use social media in their business. The majority of the use of social media is focused on product marketing or promotion, disseminating product information, and maintaining relationships with customers. Each MSME has a different degree of use of social media in their business. However, at least every MSME has one social media channel. MSME business players realize that the use of social media applications can increase access to new customers, in addition to providing opportunities to provide product or promotional information inexpensively.

The use of digital by MSME actors is quite good. Still, the service and utilization of e-commerce software need to be increased considering the various savings and increased productivity obtained from this. Expansion of reach and specifications with digital technology and e-commerce can improve the performance of MSMEs, which are later expected to impact advancing MSMEs positively.

Penta Helix is a socio-economic development model through a collaborative partnership between five sectors of academia, business, community, government, and media, which has been going well, where academics are the drafters by standardizing business processes and certifying products and skills in human resources. The business acts as an enabler that delivers ICT infrastructure by supporting changes in human resources, business processes, and developments in the digital era. The community serves as an accelerator to facilitate the adoption of business processes into the digital age as a liaison between stakeholders. The government acts as a regulator that has regulations and coordinates all stakeholders. The media plays an expanded role in supporting publications in promotion and information.

Academics are a source of knowledge with the latest and relevant concepts, theories, and businesses developed by MSME actors to gain a sustainable competitive advantage. Academics act as information for MSME actors. The company conducts business processes to create added value and maintain sustainable growth. The business operates as an enabler that delivers ICT infrastructure by supporting changes in human resources, business processes, and products in the digital era. The community also has a role in promoting MSME products or services. The society acts as an intermediary or a liaison between stakeholders to assist MSMEs in the entire process and facilitate adopting business processes into the digital era.

The Government plays a role as the owner of regulations. It is responsible for developing the Government and also has a role in coordinating the stakeholders who contribute to the development of MSMEs. In the MSME development program in Langsa City, those with a role as the Government are the Government of Manpower, the Ministry of Industry, Cooperatives

and SMEs, and the Trade Office. The part of the media in the MSME development program on the cooperative's website contains information about MSME development programs, news about MSMEs, and products sold, such as fashion, culinary (drinks/food) health, and others. The media plays a role in supporting publications in the promotion and creating a brand image in the MSME development program that supports the part of the media through the website as a medium for advertising and information. Products published on the website of MSME actors or social media such as WhatsApp, Facebook, and Instagram are included with the price.

The relationship between stakeholders in the MSME development program in Langsa City follows the relationship and role being carried out. Academics as drafters have a relationship with Business and the community due to the minimal sharing of resources with a moderate time commitment. The resources referred to here is assistance, such as capital and business information, facilities, and facilitators for training. The connection is formally established for the academic relationship with the government, and there is an ongoing commitment to sharing risks, resources, and rewards interpreted as access for academics to contribute to program development. The relationship between academics and the media is informal, and there is no sharing of the necessary resources. The main focus is the exchange of information with the use of time. Between Business with government and the community, there is sufficient commitment to sharing resources, risks, and responsibilities; Business helps provide training, capital assistance, and facilities. With more accessible access to business processes, there is no sharing of risks or responsibilities for Business and media relations.

The relationship between the communities has a decisive role in assisting the publication and promotion of MSME products through the website or other social networks such as WhatsApp, Facebook, and Instagram. One of the functions of this website is as a media to publish MSME development programs, where the website contains information about this program. Meanwhile, the relationship between the community and the government has a sufficient commitment to sharing resources, responsibilities, risks, and rewards. The government provides several accesses through training, comparative studies, and exhibitions. The government's media partner supports programs for publication and promotion in developing MSMEs. MSME business actors also use social media such as Facebook and Instagram for marketing that is managed personally. The relationship between stakeholders in collaborating on MSME development programs has not yet reached an optimal stage. However, with the collaboration between stakeholders in this program, MSMEs develop well.

CLOSING

Stakeholder of the Penta helix model in digital entrepreneurship research act as:

- a. Academics act as initiators/providers of ideas by standardizing business processes and certifying products and skills in human resources.
- b. Business actors play a role in achieving the goals that will later produce.
- c. The community acts as a means or a place that helps in development.

- d. The government in the Penta helix model plays a role as an interested party in creating conditions for fair and safe business activities for all contributing parties.
- e. Media is a source of information, promotion, and marketing tools. All stakeholders have done enough to carry out the roles considered to have prepared to realize the development of Langsa City because of the interconnected synergy between them.

The results of the SWOT analysis found that MSMEs were able to expand the reach of consumers further using digital (media) by understanding or understanding the use of media in this digital era well, which MSME actors were expected to enter later the ASEAN (AEC) market. MSME actors join e-commerce services to minimize marketing costs because marketing through social networks will be necessary, considering that most consumers use it to guide them in making profitable purchasing decisions for MSMEs. It is required to emphasize expanding its reach and specifications with digital technology and e-commerce because it can improve the performance of MSMEs.

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